

Nanopatterning reconfigurable magnetic landscapes via thermally assisted scanning probe lithography

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The search for novel tools for controlling magnetism at the nanoscale is crucial for the development of new paradigms in optics, electronics and spintronics¹⁻⁵. So far, the fabrication of magnetic devices based on magnetic nanostructures has been mainly achieved through irreversible structural or chemical modifications⁶⁻⁸. Here, we propose a new concept for creating reconfigurable magnetic nanopatterns, by crafting at the nanoscale the magnetic anisotropy landscape of a ferromagnetic layer exchange-coupled to an antiferromagnetic one. By performing a highly localized field cooling with the hot tip of a scanning probe microscope, magnetic structures, with arbitrarily oriented magnetization and tunable unidirectional anisotropy, are patterned without modifying the film chemistry and topography. The proposed technique is straightforward and combines the full reversibility and stability of exchange bias, as the same pattern can be written and reset many times, with the resolution and versatility of scanning probe lithography. This opens unforeseen possibilities for the development of novel metamaterials with finely tuned magnetic properties, as well as reconfigurable computing device architectures. In the context of magnonics, we experimentally demonstrate the local control of the spin-waves excitation in stripes patterned with the proposed method. Furthermore, we discuss the design of reconfigurable phase shifters and magnonic crystals made of a periodic arrangement of patterned stripes, allowing for the active tuning of their functionalities.

Metamaterials are composite materials in which new functionalities emerge from engineered combinations of carefully chosen and nanoscale designed material building blocks⁹⁻¹². Among these, magnetic metamaterials allow unprecedented versatility in the design of novel device architectures, exploiting the controlled propagation of the electromagnetic radiation¹³, surface plasmons¹⁴ and spin-waves¹⁵⁻¹⁷. In this context, the development of a new class of

reprogrammable magnetic metamaterials, whose functionality can be actively redesigned on demand, would open new, far reaching directions for nanomagnetism and spintronics.

So far, the fabrication of magnetic devices through the nanopatterning of magnetic materials⁶⁻⁸ has been carried out mainly using conventional lithography^{6,18} or ion irradiation^{7,8}. These techniques, in most cases, are destructive, irreversible and cannot easily produce a controlled modulation of the magnetic properties within the pattern. Beyond these methods, advanced scanning probe based lithography (SPL) is gaining attention in the scientific community for its flexibility and broad applicability with emerging new materials¹⁹.

In this paper, we propose a novel, versatile approach based on SPL, namely “thermally assisted magnetic scanning probe lithography” (*tam*-SPL), to achieve a desired and reconfigurable nano-scale engineering of the magnetic properties of a continuous film. The working principle of *tam*-SPL is the local heating and cooling of an exchange-biased ferromagnetic (FM) layer by means of the hot tip of a scanning probe microscope (SPM) brought in contact with the sample, in presence of a magnetic field. This local field cooling sets a unidirectional magnetic anisotropy in the FM, due to the exchange-coupling with the adjacent antiferromagnet (AF)²⁰. Phenomenologically, this causes a local pinning of the FM magnetization, which is observed as a shift in its hysteresis loop. In particular, we demonstrate the patterning of micro- and nano-structures with arbitrary shape, anisotropy and spin orientation. The pattern is stable at room temperature and cannot be permanently erased with magnetic fields, thus combining endurance and reconfigurability. The potential of the proposed technology lies beyond magnetic recording. With this method, novel magnetic devices and metamaterials can be fabricated in a continuous film, by reversible and fine tuning of the local magnetic anisotropy (both direction and strength). In particular, these peculiarities can be exploited in the emerging field of magnonics to fabricate

structures for the active manipulations of spin-waves. As proof-of-concept experiment, we show that a local spin-waves excitation can be obtained in reconfigurable magnetic tracks patterned by *tam*-SPL.

Magnetic patterning has been performed on a Ru(2)/IrMn(7)/CoFeB(5)/SiO₂(1000)/Si (thicknesses in nm) multilayer structure, grown by magnetron sputtering, where the IrMn/CoFeB bilayer constitutes the exchange bias system. Both the critical temperature at which the exchange bias disappears (blocking temperature T_B) and the exchange bias strength decrease with the antiferromagnetic layer (IrMn) thickness^{21,22}. We used a 7 nm IrMn layer, as this thickness ensures both a strong exchange bias and a T_B above room temperature (160°C, as shown in the Supplementary Information SI-1), allowing to perform local field cooling by scanning the heatable SPM tip. Concerning the FM, the 5 nm CoFeB thickness ensures both a sizeable exchange bias, which decreases for higher FM thickness²⁰, and a straightforward characterization of the magnetic domains by magnetic force microscopy (MFM) and magneto-optical Kerr effect microscopy (μ -MOKE). For details on the growth and magnetic characterization of the non-patterned stack, see Methods and the Supplementary Information SI-1.

The working principle of *tam*-SPL is schematically illustrated in Fig.1. The exchange bias system is first initialized by heating the whole sample above the blocking temperature, and subsequently cooling it in a uniform magnetic field H_i . This initialization sets a uniform unidirectional (UD) anisotropy axis in the FM film (see Fig. 1a), shifting its hysteresis loop by the exchange bias field (H_e) (see Fig. 1d and Methods for details). The hot tip of a SPM²³⁻²⁷ is then used to locally heat the surface of the stack above T_B (160°C) in a uniform static magnetic field $H_w = 700$ Oe, which in this particular case is chosen to be opposite to the initialization field

H_i . When the hot tip is displaced in its motion along the writing direction, the previously heated region of the AF film undergoes a “local field cooling” accompanied by a local rearrangement of the spins, due to the coupling with the underlying FM oriented in the direction of the external field H_w (Fig. 1b). Therefore, at the AF-FM interface in the patterned area, a different local exchange bias is established, which shifts the local hysteresis loop to the right by a new exchange bias field H_{ep} (Fig. 1e). Here, upon removal of the writing field H_w , the local remanent magnetization within the FM layer is determined by the new UD magnetic anisotropy. As a result, the spins of the FM in the patterned area (red arrows in Fig. 1c) are antiparallel to those of the surrounding film (yellow arrows) that switched back to the initial state.

The patterning capabilities of this technique are demonstrated in Fig. 2. 20 μm -wide square pads were first defined by optical lithography in order to facilitate navigation on the sample. Then we used *tam*-SPL to define in the pad square-, triangular- and diamond-shaped structures with different lateral sizes, from 1.5 μm to 2.5 μm (Fig. 2a), using a 3 $\mu\text{m/s}$ writing speed. The SPM heater temperature (T_H) was set to 560°C, 675°C and 765°C for squares, triangles and diamonds, respectively. These T_H values ensure that the actual temperature at the tip-sample interface is well above T_B (see Supplementary Information SI-2). H_w was set antiparallel to H_i , in order to write structures with antiparallel remanent magnetization. For more details on the patterning conditions see Methods and Supplementary Information SI-2, where a general model for the heat flow analysis developed for thermochemical (*tc*-)SPL²⁵ has been adapted to the present case. Figure 2a shows a magnetic force microscopy (MFM) image of a pad, taken at zero external field (remanent state) after *tam*-SPL, while Fig. 2b shows the topography of the same area. The opposite MFM magnetic contrast seen at the left and right edges of the patterns with respect to that at the pad edges demonstrates that regions with opposite UD anisotropy and remanent

magnetization have been written by *tam*-SPL. We remark that *tam*-SPL does not alter the morphology of the films (see Fig. 2b) and that the patterning is, therefore, “purely magnetic”. A zoomed-in MFM image of the pad area is shown in Fig. 2c. Even though diamonds have been written at much higher temperature than squares, the resulting magnetic contrast is the same for all patterned structures, thus indicating that once the blocking temperature of the system is exceeded, reproducible patterns can be obtained without the need of a precise control of T_H . As the degradation of exchange bias due to Mn interdiffusion starts to develop for temperatures above 350°C ²⁸, there is a wide range of film temperatures, from 160°C to 350°C , where patterning can be performed without causing sizeable irreversibility. This is evident from the demonstration of the reversibility of *tam*-SPL provided below (see Fig. 4 and related discussion). The fact that a very demanding control over the tip temperature is not required is crucial for future applications.

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the micromagnetic configuration giving rise to the magnetic contrast observed with MFM, we performed micromagnetic simulations (see Supplementary Information SI-7) of the square, triangle and diamond patterns, as shown in Figs. 2f, 2g, and 2h, respectively, where the black arrows indicate the orientation of the spins within the CoFeB film. With reference to a normal z -axis pointing out of the sample surface, the z -component of the magnetic force ($F_z = \mu_0 m_z \cdot (\nabla H_z)_z$) acting on a tip with magnetic moment m_z scanning 100 nm above the surface (i.e. at the typical tip-sample distance during MFM imaging in lift-mode) is also presented in Fig. 2f, g, h using a colour code. Assuming a ferromagnetic tip with a magnetic moment perpendicular to the sample surface and pointing towards it ($m_z < 0$), blue indicates attractive forces, while red repulsive ones. Referring to the polarity of the pad, set during the initialization, we can associate the dark-white contrast of MFM to the blue-red code

used in simulations (see Supplementary Information SI-7 for details). The agreement between simulations and experiments is very good for all patterns. It is worth noting that different kinds of 180 degrees domain wall (DW) can be engineered by controlling the pattern shape. The fine details of the DW structure for the different patterns are illustrated in the simulations of Figs 2f-i. In square structures, head-to-head and tail-to-tail DWs are defined on the left and right sides respectively, with the spins within the DW aligned along the wall. A different micromagnetic configuration is observed on the top and bottom sides, where the DW spins are perpendicular to the wall. In the triangle and diamond shapes, the arrangement of the spins within the wall is in between the two cases described above. By choosing the angle of the pattern side with respect to H_i and H_w , it is then possible to tune the DW magnetic configuration.

The determination of the minimum feature size achievable by performing *tam*-SPL in our multilayer system has been assessed by writing single lines with H_w antiparallel to H_i and a spacing of 2 μm (see Fig. 2d). The high resolution MFM image (Fig. 2e) of the dashed area in Fig. 2d shows that the average width of a single line, measured over a 2 μm section, is 300 nm, with a minimum of 250 nm. This demonstrates that, in this condition, the minimum spacing between lines during writing allowing to keep their individuality is on the order of 300 nm. The patterned lines present two DWs of the same topology as those observed in the horizontal sides of the squares (see Fig. 2f and 2i), with the magnetization among them which tends to be antiparallel to that in the non-patterned area. The minimum feature size and the corrugation of the lines are determined both by the domain wall width, which depends on the micromagnetic properties of the system, and by the spatial profile of the exchange bias written by *tam*-SPL. Micromagnetic simulations indicate that the width of ideal 180 degrees DWs, with the magnetization lying parallel to the wall far away from it, is in the order of 350 nm, in good

agreement with the experimental width of the lines of Fig. 2e (see Supplementary Information SI-8). The spatial profile of the exchange bias is given by the finite width of the thermal profile produced by the hot tip in the AF layer as well as by the spatial distribution of the blocking temperatures of the system, which reflects the distribution of grain sizes in the AF layer (see Supplementary Information SI-1). An improved spatial resolution and a reduced line corrugation can thus be achieved by optimizing the patterning conditions, the micro-magnetic properties of the system (e.g. the exchange bias strength, magnetocrystalline anisotropy, exchange stiffness), the grain size distribution and the thermal properties of the materials²⁹.

Concerning the spatial confinement of the thermal profile, it has already been demonstrated that, performing thermochemical (*tc*)-SPL on thermally insulating films²⁵ 15 nm features size can be achieved, which is at least comparable with state-of-the-art near-field transducers for magnetic recording technology³⁰. Regarding the writing speed, note that the crucial parameter is the time required to locally heat the sample above T_B ; further improvement, i.e., down to 1 μ s per point-feature, could be obtained with a different thermal cantilever design³¹.

In perspective, well-developed local heating technologies like those utilized in Magneto-Optical-Recording (MOR) and Heat-Assisted-Magnetic-Recording (HAMR) can be exploited for scaling up our approach. Note, however, that both the physical mechanism for magnetic writing and the application of these recording technologies are different from those of *tam*-SPL. In MOR and HAMR³², local heating in near-field geometries is employed to promote the binary switching of the magnetization, by temporary decreasing the coercive field in a granular ferrimagnetic or ferromagnetic substrate³²⁻³⁴. At variance, in *tam*-SPL, local heating is used to pattern magnetic nanostructures in an exchange bias system, by tuning the magnetic anisotropy of a continuous ferromagnetic film. Figure 3 shows that it is possible to finely tune the patterned magnetic

anisotropy landscape by controlling the tip temperatures. In Fig. 3a, we show the MFM image taken in the remanent state from square areas patterned with $T_H = 100^\circ\text{C}$, 240°C and 435°C , from the right to the left in the Figure, while applying $H_w = 700$ Oe antiparallel to H_i . When $T_H = 100^\circ\text{C}$, the local temperature of the sample is well below the blocking temperature, therefore no magnetic contrast is seen (blue square). Correspondingly, the shift of the local hysteresis loop measured with μ -MOKE along the UD anisotropy direction (Fig. 3b), approximately -50 Oe, is comparable to the one of the loop (yellow loop in Fig. 3d) measured in the adjacent non-patterned area (yellow square in Fig. 3a). The patterned area written with $T_H = 240^\circ\text{C}$ (green square) shows a magnetic contrast and the corresponding local hysteresis loop (Fig. 3c) is centred at zero magnetic fields. By increasing T_H to 435°C (red square in Fig. 3a) the local hysteresis loop is eventually shifted to the right by +50 Oe (Fig. 3d), showing the full inversion of the exchange bias field. The zero shift of the loop at 240°C results from an incomplete exchange bias inversion due to the expected distribution of T_B in the film arising from the presence of grains with different size^{20,35} (see Supplementary Information SI-1). This demonstrates the possibility to pattern complex magnetic anisotropy landscapes in a continuous multilayer by tuning the heater temperature during writing. Moreover, by setting H_w at different angles with respect to H_i , areas with UD anisotropy axis arbitrarily oriented with respect to the film UD anisotropy set during initialization can be patterned (see Supplementary Information SI-3).

The analysis of the magnetic behaviour of the patterned area under applied magnetic field, including the stability of the patterns, has been carried out by μ -MOKE. In Fig. 3e we report some frames from a video (see Supplementary Information movie S1) showing the field induced evolution of the magnetization in the patterned area of Fig. 2c (right column). The top sequence

of frames is acquired while sweeping a field parallel to the UD anisotropy axis, from -100 Oe to +100 Oe, while the bottom sequence refers to the other branch of the loop (from +100 Oe to -100 Oe). At the beginning of the top sequence, the magnetization of both patterned and unpatterned areas lies in the negative direction (dark contrast); at around -20 Oe the magnetization of the unpatterned film switches giving rise to a bright contrast, while the patterned areas remains dark. The dark contrast eventually disappears at about +50 Oe, when the switching takes place also in the patterned areas (see yellow and red hysteresis loops sketched in the middle of Fig. 3e). An analogue switching behaviour is seen in the bottom sequence. Noteworthy, the remanent configuration is the same in both sequences (see the red figures in the two sequences). Furthermore, crucial for technological applications, we have verified that the same remanent state is always recovered even after 2000 magnetization switching cycles performed with fields up to 1000 Oe (data not shown) and that the patterns are stable 6 months after writing. Indeed, the resilience of *tam*-SPL patterns arises from the stability of exchange bias, a key property exploited also in magnetic memory applications³⁶⁻³⁹. This feature can be used to implement a permanent functionality, similarly to the case of magnetic devices patterned by conventional techniques, such as lithography and ion irradiation.

The reversibility of *tam*-SPL is illustrated in Fig. 4. In Fig. 4a we show a MFM image under zero external field of two squares patterned with $T_H = 600^\circ\text{C}$ and $H_w = 700$ Oe antiparallel to H_i . Figure 4b shows the very same area after local cancellation of the left square, achieved by scanning the same area with $T_H = 600^\circ\text{C}$ in an erasing field $H_{er} = -700$ Oe, opposite to H_w . The magnetic contrast almost completely disappears in the left square, while it remains unperturbed in the right one, thus indicating that the pattern was selectively erased. In addition, Fig 4c shows that it is possible to re-write the erased area with another shape, a triangle in this case, with $T_H =$

600°C and $H_w = 700$ Oe. The pattern can also be completely erased by performing a uniform field cooling, thus providing a full flexibility in writing and reversibly configuring the magnetic anisotropy landscape.

The ability to design reconfigurable magnetic structures in continuous systems, without altering the film topography, leads to the realization of metamaterials and devices with controlled optical, plasmonic or magnonic response. In the following, we present a proof-of-concept experiment, performed by micro-focused Brillouin Light Scattering (μ -BLS), showing the potential applications of *tam*-SPL in the field of magnonics⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴. So far, magnonic devices were fabricated by physical patterning of magnetic thin-films⁴⁵, modulating their thickness⁴⁶ or, as in the case of bi-component magnetic devices, creating a periodic array made of two magnetic materials⁴⁷. Here, we propose to use our *tam*-SPL technology to pattern magnonic structures in a continuous film, thus avoiding the scattering at physical interfaces created by standard lithography and providing an easy way to introduce reconfigurability and tunability in magnonics.

The investigated sample consists of a $60 \mu\text{m} \times 60 \mu\text{m}$ squared pad, defined by optical lithography on the same multilayer structure of Fig. 2. *tam*-SPL was performed for patterning two $29 \mu\text{m}$ long and $2.6 \mu\text{m}$ wide rectangular tracks separated by $2.4 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 5a). The writing field $H_w = 600$ Oe was oriented perpendicularly with respect to H_i , in order to set a 90 degrees angle between the remanent magnetization directions inside and outside the tracks. Coplanar wave guides (CPW), oriented perpendicularly to the longitudinal direction of the tracks, were fabricated by electron-beam lithography and lift-off. The MFM image of the pattern at remanence is presented in Fig. 5b. As it can be seen, the static magnetization inside the tracks is parallel to the CPW, while it is perpendicular to the CPW in the rest of the pad. The sharp transition between patterned and non-patterned regions is marked by well-defined 90 degrees

DWs. μ -BLS measurements were performed in order to map the spin waves (SWs) intensity inside and outside the patterned tracks.

Fig. 5c shows the colour coded SWs intensity in the frequency range from 2.7 GHz to 8.3 GHz, as a function of the x -position. In order to maximize the signal, the BLS linear scan was performed in the region between the signal (S) and the ground (GND) lines of the CPW. The orange dashed lines mark the boundaries of the tracks, and the white arrows indicate the local direction of the static magnetization. The top panel of Fig. 5c shows the SWs intensity map measured at remanence. Remarkably, SWs are efficiently excited within the patterned tracks, whereas the SWs excitation efficiency is strongly reduced in the rest of the pad. A direct comparison of the BLS spectra shows that the spin-wave intensity measured inside the tracks (red squares) is about five times more intense than that measured outside (blue circles).

Such behaviour can be explained considering that, for this CPW geometry, SWs are efficiently excited mainly by the coupling between the in-plane component of the microwave field (H_{rf} in Fig. 5a) and the corresponding component of the dynamical magnetization, associated to the SWs, while the out-of-plane component of the microwave field plays a minor role. In the region within the tracks (outside the tracks) this coupling is very efficient (inefficient), because the in-plane component of the microwave field and the corresponding component of the dynamic magnetization are parallel (perpendicular)^{48,49}.

Moreover, we show that it is possible to “switch-off” the spin-wave excitation within the tracks by reorienting the magnetization with an external magnetic field. Fig. 5c (bottom panel) presents the intensity map acquired applying a magnetic field $H_{ext} = 300$ Oe along the y -axis. In this configuration, the static magnetization is aligned perpendicularly to the CPW, both inside and outside the tracks and, as a consequence, the same low spin-wave intensity is observed in the

whole pad. Note that the SWs frequency inside the tracks is about 0.5 GHz lower than in the rest of the pad (Fig. 5e), in agreement with the different orientation of the exchange bias field set inside and outside the tracks, with respect to the external applied field.

This experimental result marks the initial step for the implementation of *tam*-SPL based reconfigurable magnonic devices. In particular, in the Supplementary Information SI-6 we discuss the design of phase shifters and magnonic crystals exploiting the modulation of the refractive index seen by the SWs in patterned regions with different relative orientation of the static magnetization and of the SWs wavevector. A single stripe can be used to implement a phase shifter to be inserted in Mach-Zehnder-type interferometers, which have been proposed as basic building blocks for computing⁵⁰. In addition, periodic arrangement of stripes can be used to realize a magnonic crystal showing the emergence of the characteristic band-gaps. The bandwidth and the position of the band-gaps can be tuned by controlling the stripe width, their separation, and the width of the regions of spin rotation between the stripes. Since all these parameters can be set reversibly during patterning, our technique allows the fabrication of fully reconfigurable magnonic crystals and devices. Moreover, the active tuning of the magnonic properties after patterning can be achieved by controlling the domains extension and magnetization orientation via external magnetic fields (see Fig. 3).

In this work, we have introduced *tam*-SPL, a straightforward, single-step method for nanopatterning reprogrammable magnetic metamaterials, leaving the film chemistry and topography unperturbed. In particular, we patterned arbitrarily shaped magnetic micro- and nano-structures, which are reconfigurable and stable against external magnetic perturbations. Furthermore, we demonstrated the capability of tuning the local magnetic anisotropy giving rise

to exchange-biased structures with magnetization along an arbitrarily chosen direction, with a minimum feature size of 250 nm. In perspective, further improvement of spatial resolution can be achieved by optimizing the patterning parameters as well as the micromagnetic properties, thermal conductivity and granularity of the magnetic multilayer. Higher patterning speed could be obtained by using arrays of many heatable cantilevers⁵¹ or using near-field transducers, allowing for a highly localized and fast heating, with theoretical spot sizes down to 35 nm³⁰.

In addition, due to the extreme versatility of SPL, the magnetic patterning can be extended from continuous films to physically micro- and nano-patterned supports. Novel architectures for magnetic computing and spintronics can be envisaged, where reprogrammable magnetic metamaterials control the propagation of quasi-particles, such as domain walls in magnetic circuits, or spin-waves and surface-plasmons in magneto-plasmonic crystals. In particular, we demonstrated the local and tunable spin-waves excitation in magnetic tracks patterned by *tam*-SPL. This result paves the way to the realization of reconfigurable devices, such as spin-wave phase shifters and filters based on magnonic crystals.

Methods

Sample fabrication and characterization

Co₄₀Fe₄₀B₂₀(5 nm)/Ir₂₂Mn₇₈(7 nm)/Ru(2 nm) stacks were deposited on Si/SiO₂(1000 nm) substrates by DC magnetron sputtering using an AJA Orion8 system with a base pressure below 1×10^{-8} Torr. During the deposition, a 300 Oe magnetic field (H_G) was applied in the sample plane for setting the magnetocrystalline uniaxial (UA) anisotropy direction in the CoFeB layer and the exchange bias direction in the as-grown sample. The multilayer surface roughness measured in a $1 \mu\text{m}^2$ area is 0.15 nm rms. Squared pads with a $400 \mu\text{m}^2$ area were microfabricated by optical lithography and ion milling, allowing for the individuation of the magnetic patterns defined by *tam*-SPL. After microfabrication, in order to set a unidirectional (UD) anisotropy axis in the CoFeB film, the samples underwent a field cooling starting from 220°C (above the blocking temperature T_B) in vacuum and in a 4000 Oe magnetic field H_i applied along the UA axis of the CoFeB film. The magnetic characterization of the stacks was performed in a Microsense Vibrating Sample Magnetometer equipped with a heater for temperature dependent measurements.

tam-SPL

Thermally assisted magnetic scanning probe lithography was performed with a modified Agilent 5500 SPM system equipped with custom made silicon SPM cantilevers integrated with a Joule-heating resistive heater^{24,25,31}. Details about these thermal cantilevers and temperature calibration

are reported in Supplementary Information SI-2. A National Instruments® NI cDAQ-9178 was used for controlling and recording the current passing through the cantilever to achieve joule heating. In order to pattern arbitrary one or two dimensional geometries, such as lines, polygons and complex planar shapes, we used MATLAB® scripts in combination with the Agilent PicoView software. The magnetic patterns were written by raster-scanning the heated tip in contact mode using a linear speed of 3 $\mu\text{m/s}$. Two permanent magnets were employed for generating the uniform 700 Oe external magnetic field applied in the sample plane during patterning. An arbitrary angle between the direction of the external field and the initialization direction of the sample was set by physically rotating the sample with respect to the magnets.

MFM characterization

Magnetic force microscopy characterization of the patterned magnetic domains was performed with the same Agilent 5500 SPM system used for *tam*-SPL, equipped with a Nanosensors PPP-MFMR AFM magnetic probe. MFM imaging was performed in lift-mode, with lift-heights of 100 nm (Fig.2a-c-d Fig. 3a, Fig. 4 in the main text and Fig.S3, Fig. S4) and 30 nm (Fig. 2e).

Micro-MOKE characterization

In order to conduct investigations of the magnetization distribution at the sub-micrometer length scale we used a characterization tool based on magneto-optic Kerr effect imaging/magnetometry based on an optical wide-field polarization microscope optimized for Kerr microscopy (Evico GmbH). Arbitrary magnetic fields can be applied during observation so that domain nucleation

and magnetization processes can be observed. Indeed, the domain contrast in the image is directly sensitive to the projection of the magnetization along the sensitivity direction, which is set either parallel or perpendicular to the externally applied field. To this purpose, the microscope was equipped with a rotatable bipolar electromagnet that allows the application of a magnetic field of intensity up to 5000 Oe along an arbitrary direction in the sample plane. Two different operational modes of the microscope were used: in the first, through a high sensitivity and resolution CCD camera, magnetic contrast imaging of the sample surface was performed with a spatial resolution ~ 500 nm. In the second, the CCD camera was used as a conventional photodetector to measure the local magnetization reversal (hysteresis loops) by selecting an arbitrary region of interest (ROI) and thus a limited number of pixel. At maximum optical magnification (objective 100x followed by a 4x tube lens), each CCD pixel corresponds to an area of $15 \times 15 \text{ nm}^2$ of the sample surface. Single shot hysteresis loops of sample surface portions as small as $1 \times 1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ were measured⁵².

BLS microscopy measurements

Micro-BLS measurements have been performed focusing about 5 mW of monochromatic light, from a Diode-Pumped-Solid-State (DPSS) laser operating in the spectral line of 532 nm, with a microscope dark-field objective of large numerical aperture ($\text{NA} = 0.75$) and long working distance (4.7 mm)⁵³.

Using the same objective, a coaxial viewing system based on a collimated LED light source (455 nm wavelength), a beam expander and a CCD camera is implemented into the setup, to obtain a direct visualization of the laser spot and of the sample region under investigation. Electrical

access to the sample is achieved thanks to a specially designed ground-signal-ground (GSG) antenna with large extended pads where a DC is injected with a picoprobe.

During micro-BLS measurements the sample holder and the BLS spectrometer are controlled by the TFPDAS4-MICRO and TFPDAS4 software, developed at Kaiserslautern University⁵⁴, which provides an active stabilization of the lateral and vertical position of the sample with a precision of about 50 nm.

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Authors contribution

E.A. conceived and designed the experiments with the help of D.P., E.R. and R.B. coordinated and supervised the research work. E.A. performed the patterning experiments, MFM characterization and simulations. D.P. fabricated the samples. W.P.K. provided the thermal SPM tips. E.A., M.P., P.V. and R.B. performed the MOKE characterization. E.A. and D.P. fabricated the samples for μ -BLS measurements. M.M. and S.T. performed the μ -BLS measurements. A. P., G. C., W.P. performed the simulation of the magnonic structures. E.A., D.P., M.M., S.T., P.V., E.R. and R.B. wrote the manuscript. All the authors contributed to discussions regarding the research.

Additional Information

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Figures and legends

Figure 1. Magnetic patterning via *tam*-SPL. **a**, After initialization, the magnetization of the ferromagnetic layer (yellow arrows) is uniformly pinned in one direction by the exchange interaction with the antiferromagnetic layer (blue arrows). **b**, Sweeping a heated SPM tip on the sample surface in presence of an external magnetic field H_w produces a “local field-cooling” in the antiferromagnet (green arrows), which re-sets the exchange bias direction according to the underlying CoFeB spins (red arrows), aligned with H_w . **c**, When the external magnetic field H_w is removed, the magnetic domain configuration in the ferromagnet is stabilized by the local exchange bias. The bottom panels show the magnetic hysteresis loops before **d**, and after patterning **e**. H_e and H_{ep} indicate the opposite shift in the loops due to the exchange bias in the non-patterned and patterned areas, respectively.

Figure 2. Magnetic Force Microscope characterization and micromagnetic simulations of the patterned domain structures. MFM image **a**, and topography **b**, of the same pad after performing *tam*-SPL. The patterned domains are clearly visible in the MFM image, whereas no change in the surface topography is observed. **c**, zoomed-in MFM image of square- (top row), triangular- (center row) and diamond- (bottom row) shaped magnetic domains with size 2.5 μm (right column), 2 μm (center column) and 1.5 μm (left column). The magnetic contrast marks the domain boundaries. **d**, MFM of single lines 12 μm long. **e**, High-resolution MFM image of the

dashed rectangle in **d**, showing a minimum width of 250 nm. All MFM images are acquired under no external magnetic field. **f-i**, Micromagnetic simulation of the magnetic configuration of the patterned domains. The arrows indicate the direction of the spins, the color map is the normalized magnetic force acting on the MFM tip. The bottom panels show a zoomed view of the domain walls. Scale bars, 4 μm in **a-b**, 2 μm in **c-d**, 1 μm in **f-g-h**, 500 nm in **e**, 250 nm in **i**.

Figure 3. Tunability of the magnetic anisotropies and evolution of the patterned domains with the external magnetic field. **a**, MFM image at zero magnetic field from a non-patterned area (yellow square) and from areas patterned with $T_H = 100^\circ\text{C}$ (blue square), 240°C (green square) and 435°C (red square) and $T_w = 700$ Oe. **b,c,d**, μ -MOKE hysteresis loop corresponding to the blue, green, red and yellow squares of **a**, respectively. Starting from the initialized sample

(yellow cycle, $H_e = -50\text{Oe}$), by increasing the heater temperature, it is possible to tune the magnetic anisotropy and hence the exchange bias field (from $H_{ep} = -50\text{ Oe}$, blue cycle until $H_{ep} = +50\text{ Oe}$, red cycle). **e**, μ -MOKE images of the patterned domains (right column in Fig.2c) at different magnetic fields. In the center, the hysteresis loops from the non-patterned (yellow) and patterned (red) areas are sketched and the switching fields are marked. Scale bars, $2\ \mu\text{m}$ in **a** and **e**.

Figure 4. Writing-erasing-rewriting capability. **a**, MFM image of two squares patterned with $T_H = 600^\circ\text{C}$ and $H_w = 700\text{ Oe}$. **b**, The very same area after the erasure of the left square obtained by scanning it with $T_H = 600^\circ\text{C}$ and an erasing field $H_{er} = -700\text{ Oe}$, opposite to H_w and in the same direction of the initializing field H_i . **c**, A triangle is then re-written on the left area with $T_H = 470^\circ\text{C}$ and $H_w = 700\text{ Oe}$. Note that both the erasure and the rewriting processes leave the right square unaffected. Scale bar, $2\ \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 5. Patterning magnonic structures. **a**, Optical image of the sample, showing the coplanar waveguides (CPW) generating the Oersted field H_{rf} and the pad where the *tam*-SPL patterning was performed. The orange rectangles mark the position and shape of the structures. Scale bar: 5 μm . **b**, MFM image of the magnonic structures, consisting of two rectangular tracks, spaced by 2.4 μm . The static magnetization (white arrows) within the tracks forms a 90 degrees angle with respect to the magnetization outside. Scale bar: 4 μm . **c**, One-dimensional mapping of the spin-wave intensity measured by μ -BLS along the x -direction, between the signal (S) and the ground (GND) of the CPW. At remanence (top panel), spin-waves are efficiently excited exclusively within the patterned tracks, where the static magnetization lies parallel with respect to the CPW. By applying a magnetic field $H_{\text{ext}} = 300$ Oe as shown in panel 5a, the spin-wave excitation within the tracks is ‘switched-off’ (bottom panel). **d-e**, Spin-wave spectra extracted respectively from the top and bottom panel of **c**, inside (red squares) and outside (blue circles) the tracks. The spectra are related to the positions marked by the stars in panel **c**.